

THE FUTURE OF ADVANCED RENEWABLE ENERGY: A REVIEW ON DYSON SPHERE

Akimjonov Azimjon

University: AJOU university in Tashkent Electrical and computer engineering faculty - E24B

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Abstract. *In this paper, I review some of the available advanced renewable energy options like Dyson Sphere. How Mercury could be used for resources mining, railgun technology to overcome atmosphere could be useful and what is the Kardashev scale and how it could assist us to define our classification in the scale of the universe. This study seeks to analyze how these concepts might be used, including the specific resources and technologies needed as well as obstacles that will need to overcome through this study. With its theoretical, resource and graphical modelling dimensions, this research seeks to inform approaches that will meet the global energy needs while ensuring a sustainable human future.*

Keywords: *dyson sphere, dyson swarm, kardashev scale, railgun.*

Introduction

Finding alternative energy options is an urgent challenge of our time. And finally, with us running out of fossil fuel reserves and the climate crisis increasing alongside that, we must search for new sources of energy. Renewable energy technologies such as solar, wind and hydropower are already changing the way we power our planet but they remain far from ambitious enough to meet future needs. [12] In this study, I will examine the Dyson Sphere: a theoretical megastructure constructed to capture all of the power output of a star and an extreme but scintillating prognostication for humanity's fate.[5]

The Dyson Sphere is an idea that inspires consideration of space-based energy solutions as a possibility for meeting future energy needs. While this idea may be a long way off — science fiction might just be enough to capture the attention of powerhouse source— competition until then — it would allow for virtually limitless energy sourcing from stars, offering an unprecedented answer to our global power needs. This paper explores how feasible a Dyson Sphere actually is, and the drastic effect it would have on future human energy output. In this work I will also consider the technical and logistical issues entailed in building such a megastructure, as well as its theoretical foundation.

The Kardashev Scale: A Vision of Energy Evolution

The history of human civilization has always been closely shaped by how we harness and use energy. Towards more advanced energy solutions, it's important to consider how far humanity could potentially go when making use of available resources. The future could be imagined within one of the most thought-provoking frameworks for doing so, called the Kardashev Scale, developed in 1964 by Russian astrophysicist Nikolai Kardashev.[4]

The Kardashev Scale breaks civilizations into three types—the amount of energy each can consume defines them:

$$K = \frac{\log_{10} W - 6}{10} \quad (\text{Sagan's finer classification})$$

Type I Civilization – Planetary Level

At this stage, a Type I civilization is one that is capable of exploiting and utilizing all available energy on their home planet. This includes energy from fossil fuels, wind, solar power, geothermal sources, and energy from ocean currents. For the Earth, the total amount of energy

received from the Sun is about $1.74 \cdot 10^{17}$ watts. Typically, the civilizations belonging to this category are the ones that have an energy consumption within the range of 10^{16} to 10^{17} watts

Type II Civilization – Stellar Level

At present, human energy consumption is of the order of 10^{13} watts. A civilization that can harvest the complete energy output of its star and, in other words, control the energy radiated by its Sun is classified as Type II. Value of the solar energy output is approximately $3.828 \cdot 10^{26}$ watts. One of the hypothetical constructions helping to achieve this consumption of energy might be a Dyson Sphere- a megastructure to surround a star and capture all the energy.

Type III Civilization – Galactic Level

Type III civilization that can control the energy output of an entire galaxy. The energy radiated by the Milky Way galaxy is estimated to be around $8 \cdot 10^{36}$ watts.

The Path Forward: From Type 0 to Type I

While humankind is now at the very low end of energy consumption—far below Type I—most of its future involves striving to attain that level. The attainment of Type I status calls for the adaption of renewable sources of energy, upgrading technological infrastructure, and making more efficient use and distribution of energy in every way possible. Transition to renewable sources, development of space-based energy sources, and, perhaps, creation of megastructures such as a Dyson Sphere may one day give rise to civilizations that can attain Type II or even Type III status.

Year	Energy production			Value on the Kardashev scale
	exajoules /year	P, TW	tons of oil equivalent /year	
1900	21	0,67	500 000 000	0,58
1970	190	6,0	4 500 000 000	0,67
1985	290	9,2	6 900 000 000	0,69
1995	360	12	8 700 000 000	0,70
2000	420	13	10 000 000 000	0,71
2010	510	16	12 100 000 000	0,72
2030 (forecast)	680	22	16 300 000 000	0,73

The real question is, what is the Dyson Sphere, and how do we begin building one? Freeman Dyson (yes, the very same Dyson of vacuum fame) first proposed the idea back in 1960, as the most far-reaching concept ever for collecting the same amount of energy. It's a megastructure concept hypothetical, of course that would surround a star in its entirety and allow it to collect and use energy in the most efficient way possible for the requirements of an ultra-highly-developed civilization (In Kardashev's scale by 1964, this civilization stands as second type). [2]

In its most basic form, the Dyson Sphere is often imagined as a massive, spherical shell that surrounds a star and captures the most of its energy output.

However, while the idea of a solid spherical shell around a star is often thought in science fiction, it is more likely that any real world implementation would look like a Dyson Swarm[3] a huge number of smaller structures or solar collectors orbiting the star. These structures would work as union to collect solar energy, which could then be transmitted for use, either in space or

sent back to the home planet via energy beams, as in futuristic concepts of space-based energy transmission.

Building a Dyson Sphere, or even a Dyson Swarm, presents enormous technological, engineering, and material challenges. Firstly, the scale of the project far exceeds current engineering capabilities. Surrounding a star like the Sun with a solid shell would require a structure with a diameter of millions of kilometers, which exceeds current technological capabilities.

Moreover, the energy and resources required to build such a structure are enormous. Even if we were able to construct a Dyson Swarm, we would still need a method of manufacturing and assembling these components in the space. Mining asteroids or even entire planets for the necessary materials might be a potential solution.[3][10]

The goal of this paper aims to explore the feasibility of building a Dyson Sphere, beginning with an analysis of the materials, energy resources, and technologies that would be used to construct such a megastructure.

Materials and methods:

Step 1: How to collect energy from the Sun

To begin our roadmap for constructing a *Dyson Swarm*, we need to separate the project into smaller, manageable steps, starting with the first concept: *how to collect energy from the Sun*. While many concepts exist, according to many scientists (*such as George Dvorsky*) one of the most feasible and effective ideas involves the use of *space mirrors* to reflect and focus sunlight to orbital stations, which would then convert energy into forms of lasers or microwaves to translate them back to Earth or other stations.[3][10]

The most ideas and concepts are taken from *Dvorsky, G. (2012, March 20). “How to build a Dyson sphere in five steps.”*

Panels for the Dyson Swarm: Design and Materials

The panels for the Dyson Swarm need to be designed with both efficient reflection and durability, capable of coping with the extreme condition of space. One of the most effective (according to Syron Optics company) designs is “Parabolic” that can focus all the lights in one point.[11]

Fig 1: Parabolic Panel Design

Parabolic Panel Design

1. Shape and Geometry:

- **Parabolic Shape:** Each panel would have a parabolic form to focus sunlight to a specific target area. This design enhances the efficiency of light reflection and concentration compared to flat or other shaped panels.
2. **Opening Mechanism:**
- **Collapsible Parabolic Design:** Panels would use a collapsible design for efficient storage during launch process.
 - **Support Structure:** Lightweight tubes made of carbon composites or aluminum would maintain the parabolic shape when it is deployed.
 - **Electromagnetic Actuators or Inflatable Mechanism:** These would assist in unfolding and shaping the panels.
3. **Materials:**
- **Body:** The main structure of the panel would be aluminum, for its strength and cost.
4. **Thermal Protection:**
- The rear side of the panel would use a highly reflective material (e.g., **gold** or **ceramic-based coatings**) to minimize heat absorption. These methods are suggested by NASA[8]
5. **Operational Features:**
- **Energy Collection:** The parabolic design allows light to be directed to receiving stations, where it can be converted to microwaves or lasers to easily transmit energy to Earth or other places.

Advantages of the Parabolic Design:

- **Enhanced Efficiency:** The parabolic shape concentrates sunlight.
- **Compact Storage:** Foldable parabolic design occupy minimal space during launch and being cost effective during deployment.
- **Durability in Space:** Materials and design provides resistance to extreme temperatures, radiation and impacts of space (According to researches).

Experimental model of such panel is available here: <https://p3d.in/NjUAU/spin>

Step 2: Resource Procurement – Mining Mercury for Construction Materials

To build the vast number of solar collectors, mirrors, and other components for the Dyson Swarm, we will need huge amount of resources—**quadrillions of tons according to calculations id they are built as lightly as possible**[14]. These materials will need to come from somewhere beyond Earth, because those resources available on our planet are insufficient for such an enormous project. The most feasible option for mining is **Mercury** — the closest planet to the Sun and the best option for mining according to **RealClearScience** and **Ross Pomeroy** (Journalist and Writer of scientific articles).[10] Here’s why:

1. **Mercury’s distance to the Sun:**
 - **No Atmosphere:** Mercury's low gravity and lack of atmosphere make it ideal for resource extraction and transportation.

2. **Resource Abundance:**

○ **Mineral Wealth:** Mercury is rich in essential resources for construction, such as *nickel, iron, magnesium, and silicon*—materials that will be crucial for building our solar panels, reflectors, and other components.

3. **Efficient Transportation to Space:**

○ **Avoiding Earth’s Gravity Well:** Launching materials from Earth would require a lot of amount of energy due to Earth’s gravity. Even with all the available resources and fuel, we would only be able to launch as much weight as mountain Everest’s.

Step 3: Efficient Launch System – Railgun Cannon for Space Transport

Given the scale of the Dyson Swarm and the need to transport quadrillions of tons of materials, traditional rocket launches would be really expensive. Instead, we would need to find much more efficient and scalable method of transporting objects from Mercury into space. Such a method has been proposed by many scientists and considers usage of a technology called *Railgun* [1][7]

The Electromagnetic Cannon (Mass Driver):

1. **Principle of Operation:**

○ Mass drivers use electromagnetic forces to launch objects into space, offering an alternative method of launching to rockets.

2. **Advantages over Rockets:**

○ **Energy Efficiency:** Unlike chemical rockets that burn fuel, the mass driver would operate using electricity—potentially harnessed from the Sun via solar panels that we may set up on Mercury's surface

3. **Railgun:**

○ **Track Design:** The Railgun would need to be built on Mercury, and the launch track could be long enough to achieve escape velocity. The railgun coils would generate acceleration to send panels into orbit (or strictly towards sun).

Step 4: Automation and Human Presence – Mercury’s Robotic Workforce

The construction of a Dyson Swarm requires a massive workforce. However, sending large numbers of humans to another planet, especially to Mercury with its extreme conditions, would not only be dangerous but also highly dumb idea. Therefore, to undertake our monumental mission, we would rely heavily on *automation*, and *a minimal human presence*. Robots will be extracting resources from Mercury's surface, including metals like *nickel, iron, and magnesium*, as well as rare elements needed for building materials.[10]

Calculations:

There is some data about how we can launch an object from Mercury:

- Energy needed:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$$

m – mass of the object (I will calculate everything for 100 kg objects)

v – velocity of the object

- Velocity needed:

We have to find a velocity to escape the planet's gravitational field and become a satellite of the sun. It is called *second space velocity*:

$$v = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}}$$

G – Gravitational constant ($6.6743 \times 10^{-11} \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{kg}^2$)

M – Mass of the object we are going to escape (Mercury mass = $3.3 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ kg}$)

r – radius of that object we are going to escape (Mercury radius = 2 439,7 km)

Fig 2: Energy to launch an object for different planets

Mercury itself is mainly consists of 30% silicate and 70% metal, mainly iron or iron oxides, so these would be the most used materials. The mass of Mercury is $3.3022 \times 10^{23} \text{ kg}$; assuming 50% of this mass could be transformed into reflective surfaces (with the remaining material made into heat engines/solar cells), and that these would be placed in Mercury’s orbit. The reflective pieces would have a mass of

$$\frac{\text{mass} * \text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} = \frac{0.5 * 3.3022 * 10^{23}}{\text{area of the structure}}$$

From “Eternity in six hours: intergalactic spreading of intelligent life and sharpening the Fermi paradox” Armstrong, S., & Sandberg, A. (2012).[1]

Fig 3: Mass of panels

Let's create a formula to account for the various efficiencies involved in transmitting energy from the mirrors to Earth. The energy we get on Earth can be calculated as:

$$E_{on\ earth} = N * k_1 * k_2 * \frac{1361 * S}{y^2}$$

where:

- $E_{on\ earth}$ — the energy received on Earth (in watts).

- N — the number of mirrors in the Dyson Swarm.
- k_1 — the percentage of energy absorption efficiency of the mirrors, including losses)
- k_2 — the percentage of energy loss during transmission, for example via microwaves or lasers.
- 1361 — the solar energy intensity in watts per square meter, the amount of solar energy received at 1 meter².
- S — the area of one panel (in square meters). For this calculation, let's assume $S=10$ m.
- y — the distance from the Sun to the mirrors (**A.U.**).

Step 2: Substituting the Known Values

Let's assume we have the following parameters:

- Number of mirrors, N : Let's take $N=10,000$ mirrors.
- Energy absorption percentage for the mirrors, k_1 : Let $k_1=0.8$ (80% of the energy is transmitted to energy transferring stations).
- Energy absorption during transmission to Earth, k_2 : Let $k_2=0.8$ (80% of the energy is transmitted to Earth from stations).

For the area of each panel, we have:

$$S = 10m^2$$

And for the distance, I'll use y as a variable for now.

Step 3: Calculate the Energy

Substitute the known values into the formula:

$$E_{on\ earth} = 10,000 * 0.8 * 0.8 * \frac{1361 * 10}{y^2} \text{ watts}$$

Simplifying this expression:

$$E_{on\ earth} = 10,000 * 0.64 * \frac{1361 * 10}{y^2} \text{ watts}$$

$$E_{on\ earth} = 8,704,000 * \frac{1}{y^2} \text{ watts}$$

Step 4: Result

Thus, the energy received on Earth from the Dyson Swarm would be:

$$E_{on\ earth} = 8,704,000 * \frac{1}{y^2} \text{ watts}$$

Where y is the distance from the Sun to the mirrors in **A.U.**. The closer mirrors are to the Sun, the more energy is collected and vica versa.

Choosing the optimal distance for placing the mirrors is important for us. If we attempt to place them at the same distance from the Sun as Mercury's orbit (between 3.7 and 4.0 AU), there is a

risk that Mercury's gravitational force will be strong enough to attract the mirrors and cause them to collide with the planet. On the other hand, if we place the mirrors closer to the Sun, (at a distance less than 3.7 AU), the panels would be subject to receive overheating and damage due to the huge solar radiation.

Ideally, we want to place them at one of the Lagrange points.[6] However, these points either are too close to the Sun (L1), too close to Earth (L2), or too far from the Sun (L4 and L5). That is why, an optimal solution would be to place the mirrors at a distance of approximately **0.5 AU** from the Sun. This distance will balance the need for efficient energy collection and still will avoid the overheating from the sun radiation. Let’s put this into our formula:

$$E_{on\ earth} = 8,704,000 * \frac{1}{0.5^2} \text{ watts}$$

$$E_{on\ earth} = 34,816,000 \text{ watts (with only 10 000 mirrors)}$$

For a real **Dyson swarm** we would use much more. With 100,000,000 mirrors, the system could theoretically generate approximately 348 billion watts of energy."

Fig 4: Energy Output for different conditions

Fig 5: Energy Output for different distances from sun

After the first panel is launched, its energy can be used to construct a new one. Then, the energy from these two panels can be used to build four more panels, and so on, following an exponential growth.[13] This process allows us to keep a rapid expanding network of panels, each new generation will create more, leading to a system that grows exponentially over time.

Fig 6: Energy Output per doubling period

All codes for graphs could be found here: <https://github.com/stmustbk/Datas>

Discussion

Based on our results, it is easy to conclude that the energy we could harness from our theoretical Dyson Sphere-like structure, consisting of 1 billion panels with an area of 10 square meters each, would be approximately 3,000 times greater than the power output of the world's most powerful nuclear reactor (1.5 GW) which is located in Japan and known as the Kashiwazaki-Kariwa Nuclear Power Plant.

Using the growth of panel numbers, we can assume that stopping at just 1 billion panels would be a shortsighted decision, especially considering our plans to dismantle an entire Mercury! Given the rapid increase in the number of panels proportional to the energy they generate, we can conclude that the more panels we have, the easier it will be to further expand their production. Ultimately, by assembling enough panels, we will harness such an enormous amount of energy that we can eliminate pollution and fully transition to renewable energy solutions. The absence of a need for other energy sources will have a colossal positive impact on Earth, improving the planet on a massive scale and ensuring its preservation for future generations.

Conclusion

While the concept of taking energy from the sun via Dyson Swarm remains far from realization, it still keeps potential to help humanity to step into the next phase of energy development and supply.

- I. Though technological and resources' related challenges remain significant, the creation of such a project offers an inspiring idea for the future of clean and virtually limitless energy production.
- II. The Dyson Swarm represents more than just a hypothetical renewable energy solution—it provides us with limitless potential of renewable energy to reshape our civilization and lead humanity toward a bright future of sci-fi writer's dreams.

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